

Fig. 6. Long-term monthly of temperature (a) and precipitation (b) in Rasht district to relation to climatic norms of temperature and precipitation

Conclusions. It has been established that the main factors determining the processes of migration and precipitation of heavy metals are the acid-base and oxidation-reduction conditions of the aquatic environment.

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THE IMPACT OF CLIMATIC FACTORS ON DENUDATION AND ACCUMULATION PROCESSES IN THE LESSER CAUCASUS

Abstract. *The Lesser Caucasus, one of the most complex mountainous systems of Azerbaijan, stands out with its diverse geomorphological and climatic conditions. This diversity allows for a clearer observation of the influence of climatic factors on the dynamic development of the relief. Climate components such as temperature, precipitation, frost-thaw events, and wind directly affect the scale and nature of denudation and accumulation processes. This study analyzes the mechanisms through which climatic factors influence geomorphological processes in the Lesser Caucasus and investigates the outcomes and practical significance of these interactions.*

Keywords: *Lesser Caucasus, climate, denudation, accumulation, geomorphological processes, temperature, precipitation, frost-thaw, relief*

ВЛИЯНИЕ КЛИМАТИЧЕСКИХ ФАКТОРОВ НА ПРОЦЕССЫ ДЕНУДАЦИИ И АККУМУЛЯЦИИ НА МАЛОМ КАВКАЗЕ

Аннотация. Малый Кавказ, являющийся одной из самых сложных горных систем Азербайджана, выделяется своим разнообразием геоморфологических и климатических условий. Это разнообразие позволяет более чётко проследить влияние климатических факторов на динамическое развитие рельефа. Такие климатические компоненты, как температура, осадки, процессы замерзания-оттаивания и ветер, непосредственно влияют на масштаб и характер процессов денудации и аккумуляции. В данной работе анализируются механизмы воздействия климатических факторов на геоморфологические процессы в пределах Малого Кавказа, а также рассматриваются результаты этих взаимодействий и их практическое значение.

Ключевые слова: Малый Кавказ, климат, денудация, аккумуляция, геоморфологические процессы, температура, осадки, замерзание-оттаивание, рельеф.

The role of climatic factors in the formation and dynamics of geomorphological processes is one of the main research directions in modern physical geography and landscape science. Climatic elements such as temperature, precipitation, wind, and solar radiation influence the formation, transformation, and development of relief forms directly or indirectly. From this perspective, the Lesser Caucasus region—with its complex orographic structure and variable climatic conditions—serves as a favorable research area for studying climate-geomorphology interactions.[3]

The Lesser Caucasus features a complex geomorphological structure, comprising high, middle, and low mountainous relief forms. Within this structure, denudation (the wearing down, breaking, and washing away of rocks) and accumulation (the deposition and collection of materials) processes are actively observed. The intensity and spatial characteristics of these processes are closely linked to the climatic factors affecting the region.[1]

In recent decades, climate change—particularly variations in precipitation patterns, warming trends, and an increase in extreme weather events—has directly impacted the intensity and manifestations of geomorphological processes in the Lesser Caucasus. Under such conditions, processes like soil erosion, river incision, landslides, and downslope material transport have intensified in mountainous areas. These changes affect not only natural landscapes but also the stability of agricultural lands and infrastructure.

The main objective of this study is to scientifically analyze the mechanisms by which climatic factors (temperature, precipitation, wind, and frost-thaw events) influence denudation and accumulation processes in the Lesser Caucasus. To achieve this, the region’s climate conditions and geomorphological characteristics are examined, and the current intensity and spatial distribution of these processes are evaluated.[5]

Denudation and accumulation processes play a leading role in the geomorphological evolution of the Lesser Caucasus. The region’s complex relief, climatic variability, and geological structure contribute to the widespread occurrence and diverse forms of these processes.

Denudation mainly occurs through physical and partly chemical weathering. In mountainous areas, sharp temperature changes and frost-thaw events in winter intensify physical weathering. This is particularly evident in the high elevations of the Murovdagh, Zangezur, and Karabakh ranges. Chemical denudation is more prominent in areas with carbonate rocks and high precipitation—for example, the Dashalty and Hakari river basins.[1]

Accumulation occurs through the transportation and deposition of denudation-derived materials by rivers, runoff, and, to a lesser extent, wind. Alluvial and proluvial deposits are widespread in the mountain rivers of the Lesser Caucasus. In the valleys of the Kurekchay, Tartar, and Bargushad rivers, alluvial layers composed of silt, sand, and gravel have formed. Proluvial cones appear at the foot of slopes due to temporary runoff.[2]

The role of climatic factors in the geomorphological development of the Lesser Caucasus is of great importance. The region’s complex relief and altitudinal zones create conditions for climate elements—temperature, precipitation, frost-thaw events, and wind—to have varied impacts on geomorphological processes, especially denudation and accumulation.

Temperature regimes in the Lesser Caucasus vary widely: summers are hot and winters mild

in the low mountain zones, while winters are severe and summers short and cool in the high mountains. These thermal differences increase physical weathering due to expansion and contraction of rocks. As elevation increases, frost-thaw events become more frequent and intense, particularly in the Murovdagh and Zangezur ranges, leading to slope collapse, rock disintegration, and intensified soil erosion.[4]

Table 1

Climatic Factor	Denudation Process Effects	Accumulation Process Effects	Remarks/Examples
Temperature	- Enhances physical weathering by causing thermal expansion/contraction - Increases rock fracturing and cracking	- Influences phase changes in precipitation that indirectly affect sediment transport and deposition	- Lower mountainous zones: warm summers and mild winters - High mountains: severe winters, intensifying weathering
Precipitation	- Promotes water erosion and slope runoff - Accelerates river incision	- Facilitates the deposition of sediments (alluvial layers) in river valleys - Enhances material accumulation in low rainfall areas	- Western slopes receive 800–1200 mm annually, increasing erosional activity - Eastern foothill areas receive less rainfall, favoring deposition
Frost-Thaw Events	- Intensifies physical weathering through repeated freeze-thaw cycles - Causes rock fragmentation and slope collapse	- Contributes indirectly by increasing sediment supply available for deposition	- Primarily observed above 2000 m (e.g., in the Qarakilse and Dalidagh massifs)
Wind	- Causes aeolian abrasion that enhances surface weathering	- Transports and deposits rock particles, aiding in the formation of alluvial deposits	- Most noticeable on bare and sparsely vegetated slopes, such as those found in Gadabay and Dashkasan districts

Precipitation distribution also varies with relief. The western slopes (especially in Tovuz, Gadabay, and Shamkir districts) receive higher rainfall—up to 800–1200 mm annually. In such areas, water erosion, slope runoff, and landslides are more active. In contrast, the eastern foothill areas (e.g., border zones of Aghdam, Tartar, and Barda districts) receive less rainfall, where accumulation processes—deposition of rock and soil materials—predominate.[5]

Frost-thaw events are mostly observed above 2000 m, especially in the Qarakylsa and Dalidagh massifs. Here, temperature fluctuations and a high number of freezing days cause rocks to break along micro-cracks, leading to gradual slope disintegration through physical denudation.

Wind and aeolian processes are more commonly observed in bare areas with weak vegetation cover, particularly in foothill zones with temporarily arid microclimates. In such regions, wind transports and deposits rock particles, forming aeolian denudation and accumulation features. These processes can be seen on the bare slopes of Gadabay and Dashkasan districts.[3]

In conclusion, the impact of climatic factors on the geomorphological environment in the Lesser Caucasus is zonal in nature and closely linked to elevation. Understanding this interaction is essential for grasping the morphodynamic evolution of the region.

This study has revealed that climatic factors play a decisive role in the formation and development of geomorphological processes in the Lesser Caucasus. The region’s complex topography, diverse elevation zones, and climatic zonality contribute to the spatial variability of these impacts.

The Influence of Climatic Factors on Denudation and Accumulation Processes in the Lesser Caucasus[1,5]

Key findings can be summarized as follows:

- Temperature and precipitation differences—especially between high mountainous and low foothill zones—determine the intensity and form of denudation and accumulation processes in the

Lesser Caucasus.

- Frost-thaw events, mainly occurring above 2000 meters, are a primary source of physical weathering, leading to slope collapse and rock disintegration.
- Uneven precipitation distribution results in water erosion, landslides, and the deposition (accumulation) of river-transported materials across various relief forms.
- Wind and evaporation factors contribute to the development of aeolian processes in arid and vegetation-sparse areas, forming depositional cones and dust-accumulation zones.

The scientific and practical significance of these findings is as follows:

- Geomorphological hazards (erosion, landslides, soil flow) can be assessed in advance when planning engineering and land reclamation projects in the region;
- The interaction between relief and climate can be considered in the planning of agricultural and land-use systems to help prevent soil erosion;
- In the context of climate change, appropriate ecological and landscape protection measures can be developed by accounting for the potential intensification of geomorphological processes.

Thus, a comprehensive analysis of the geomorphological impact of climatic factors is of special relevance not only from a scientific standpoint but also in terms of sustainable regional development and the proper management of natural resources.

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ИҚЛИМ ЎЗГАРИШИ ВА УНИНГ АТРОФ-МУҲИТГА ТАЪСИРИНИ ОПТИМАЛЛАШТИРИШДА ЎСИМЛИКЛАРНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИНИ БАҲОЛАШ

***Аннотация.** Ушбу тадқиқотда ўсимликларнинг иқлим ўзгариши ва унинг атроф-муҳитга бўлган таъсирини оптималлаштиришдаги аҳамияти кўриб чиқилган. Ўсимликлар фотосинтез жараёни ва микроиқлим ҳосил қилиши орқали иқлим ўзгаришларининг салбий таъсирини камайтиришда катта аҳамиятга эга. Шунингдек, ўсимликларнинг ҳарорат режимини тартибга солиш қобилияти, шаҳарлар ва қишлоқ ҳудудларида микроиқлимни яхшилашда ҳам муҳим ўрин тутди. Тадқиқотда асосий эътибор экологик жиҳатдан барқарор бўлган, "яшил инфратузилма" ни яратиш имкониятларига қаратилган. Бу инфратузилмалар иқлим ўзгаришларига самарали қарши туриш ва геотизимларга бўлган салбий таъсирни минималлаштиришга ёрдам беради.*

***Калит сўзлар:** глобал иситиш, яшил иқтисодиёт, яшил макон, арид минтақа, эвапотранспирация, экологик сиёсат, альбедо, моделлаштириш.*

ОЦЕНКА ЗНАЧЕНИЯ РАСТЕНИЙ В ОПТИМИЗАЦИИ ИЗМЕНЕНИЙ КЛИМАТА И ИХ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ НА ОКРУЖАЮЩУЮ СРЕДУ

***Аннотация.** В данном исследовании рассмотрена роль растений в оптимизации воздействия изменения климата и его воздействия на окружающую среду. Растения играют важную роль в снижении негативных последствий изменения климата через процесс фотосинтеза и формирования микроэкосистем. Также способность растений регулировать температурный режим имеет ключевое значение для улучшения микроэкосистем в городах и*